

COAR NARRATIVE SERIES

The Untapped Public Value of Open Access Repositories

Confederation of Open Access Repositories

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Introduction

After many years of sustained investment, there are now [thousands of open access repositories](#) from all around the world that collect and preserve valuable research outputs. An analysis of roughly half the repositories in COAR's International Repository Directory, for example, found that 3,489 repositories, interrogated using OAI-PMH, contained close to 340 million records spanning a wide variety of research outputs such as articles, datasets, code, and reports. These repositories are open by design and were built to provide barrier-free access to research outputs for both humans and machines. Together, they form a key pillar of global research infrastructure, enabling researchers and the public to access the collective knowledge produced through scholarly research.

Over the past two decades, the case for open access repositories has mainly focused on benefits for the research enterprise, including accelerating new discoveries, supporting career advancement, and increasing academic visibility (Romano & Boggio, 2024). This framing has contributed to the successful establishment of numerous declarations and policies requiring publicly funded research to be made freely available, such as the Budapest Declaration (2002), UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science (2021), Plan S (cOAlition S, 2018), and the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP, 2022). However, one of the most important benefits of open access - public access to research outputs - has typically been overlooked.

Research knowledge beyond the academy

The idea that scholarly research should contribute to societal and industrial advancement is not new, but it has typically been pursued through activities such as commercialisation or knowledge mobilisation; processes that seek to transform research evidence into actionable products, policies, and practices. However, a significant and growing body of evidence suggests that when research outputs are made openly available directly to the public, they are used in a myriad of ways by many diverse communities.

Alperin's 2015 dissertation, for example, found extensive use of Latin American open access journal portals (SciELO and RedALyC) by students, non-academics, and public users. Similarly, an analysis of Finland's Journal.fi revealed that only 36% of users were researchers, while the remainder included students, private citizens, other experts, and teachers (Pölonen et al., 2021). Anecdotal evidence about the use of repositories reflects similar patterns to those observed with open access journals. While most repositories do not actively collect information about their users, those that do, report a wide variety of audiences and motivations for accessing content.

The Harvard DASH repository, for instance, introduced a “DASH Stories” feature in 2012, inviting readers to share how they are using or benefiting from the open access resources available in the repository. The feedback is compelling: over 9,000 contributions from physicians, patients, teachers, entrepreneurs, and citizens across the globe offering a rich portrait of public engagement with open access resources. MIT Libraries, the Digital Repository of Ireland, and the University of Edinburgh, each of which has also collected user narratives, have amassed similar testimonial evidence, highlighting the considerable but often under-recognised value of research outputs when they are made openly available in a repository.

The following examples illustrate how open access can empower individuals in both their professional and personal lives:

From a user of Harvard’s Dash Stories:

“I returned to India in 2005 to work with slum dwellers of Mumbai and Tribals of Palghar District, working with community youth on research based actions, community development, and strengthening local democracy. This kind of educational literature will definitely help us to understand the behavioural patterns of the poor and create strategies which will be more acceptable to them, thus bringing meaningful positive changes in their lives. So Thank YOU very much for making this facility available to us working in the global South. For the most part we can not afford JStor kinds of websites. Thank YOU! “

From a journalist and user of DIGITAL.CSIC repository:

“In our case, the content that is openly accessible through the DIGITAL.CSIC portal has served as a source for documenting some of the articles published on our website. Having the ability to find the necessary data through studies backed by professionals in their field and made available online openly and for free is, I believe, one of the most important—and, why not say it, fundamental—ways to raise awareness today about a wide range of topics, which has been of great help to us.”

The role of repositories in maintaining public trust

Meanwhile, mistrust of scientific claims is growing among some communities as knowledge is increasingly mediated through social media and other digital platforms where it can be misinterpreted or manipulated for political or commercial purposes (Gallup, 2024; Edelman, 2024). The public faces genuine challenges in distinguishing between factual information and misinformation, especially since misinformation frequently adopts the same conventions as legitimate content, particularly in an AI-dominated information environment.

Despite this skepticism, scientists still enjoy relatively high levels of public confidence. Cologna et al. (2025), surveying more than 71,000 respondents across 68 countries, found considerable trust in scientists, with 83% of respondents saying researchers

should communicate more with the public. Similarly, Pew's 2024 survey reports that three-quarters of Americans trust scientists, ranking them well above journalists and elected officials (Tyson & Kennedy, 2024).

In this context, repositories - which provide open access to results of research created by the researchers - are well positioned to play a key role in maintaining and cultivating public trust. Their credibility is further bolstered by the fact that repositories are usually managed by academic or nonprofit institutions, are rarely profit-driven, and typically operate under transparent governance structures (L'Hours et al., 2019). Repositories with institutional affiliations and scope bring with them an extra layer of legitimacy, since they accept content only from their faculty and students and are therefore at lower risk of receiving fraudulent submissions. This combination of institutional stewardship and open access to primary sources provides a chain of provenance that links research outputs to accountable organisations, establishing repositories as highly trusted sources of information. Moreover, repositories are a logical extension of the civic mission of a university by providing direct access to their research production to their communities (Moore et al., 2020).

Public-facing functionalities

Despite their unmistakable value for the public, repositories were not originally designed with a public audience in mind, but rather for research communities, and therefore have not been optimised for the public user. The utility of repositories could be significantly enhanced through the adoption of more public-facing features, such as plain-language summaries, clearer provenance signals, and more systematic and seamless connections with the intermediary services, such as search engines and chat bots, that are widely used by the public for information seeking.

Plain language summaries are one well-established method for improving non-expert consumption of research information, but they have not yet been widely employed by repositories. Plain language summaries typically communicate the significance of a scholarly research article in jargon-free language. They are already being produced by many biomedical publishers who have found them very effective and widely used. A study of eLife's plain-language digests, for instance, found they were very valuable for researchers in gaining cross-disciplinary insights (King et al., 2017). Notably, the primary users were researchers working outside their own specialties. bioRxiv, an open access preprint repository in the biomedical sciences, launched a pilot project in 2023 that was aimed at using LLMs to increase accessibility of content on bioRxiv. Every bioRxiv preprint was accompanied by three AI-generated summaries, each created for a different kind of reader: (1) someone with little or no scientific training; (2) a scientist with expertise in a different field; and (3) someone whose expertise equals the author's.

In 2024, the pilot was extended, improving the AI-generated summaries and allowing authors to edit the summaries. Given the rapid improvements of AI tools for summarising information, plain language summaries (in text or video format) could be a very useful enhancement for repositories in the near future and greatly improve their value to non-expert readers (Lavoie, 2025).

Provenance and credibility markers are another important aspect of ensuring public trust. The role of the repository as a trusted reference point for users is significantly enhanced when certain infrastructure-level conditions are in place. Well-structured and comprehensive metadata, a commitment to long-term preservation, persistent linking via PIDs, connections between related resources, and machine-friendly formats and APIs are all essential for providing users with the context about the resource and its dependability. Without these components, the chain of trust can break down. Moreover, in an increasingly decentralised scholarly ecosystem and with new innovations being adopted (such as preprint sharing and the Publish, Review, Curate model of publishing), information about versioning and the review status of a resource will become even more important, as will greater transparency of peer reviews.

Integrating repository resources into discovery services

Although some users will visit repositories directly, members of the general public are more likely to consume information via search engines, AI assistants / chat bots, news aggregators, health portals, and so on. In this scenario, repositories can still play an important role in the broader epistemic environment by establishing measures to allow the claims circulating in the ecosystem to be traced back to their original source in a hosted repository. In doing so, repositories can serve as verification platforms underpinning the information systems that citizens are accustomed to using in their daily lives.

Since general web crawlers often bypass established repository metadata protocols (COAR, 2025), the provenance information contained in the repository is often not reflected in these public-facing systems. To support these scenarios, repositories should provide provenance and other contextual information in a variety of easily consumable ways for both machines and humans (in addition to maintaining well-established protocols such as OAI-PMH). For example, this information should be included on the repository landing pages where structured HTML can easily be crawled. Lightweight yet powerful approaches, including “signposting”, should be deployed to enable fast and frictionless consumption of structured data (Uthayakumar, 2026). Offering a variety of machine-friendly options to obtain relevant metadata and other information about the resource from the repository significantly increases the likelihood that it will be reflected in the discovery layer.

At the same time, there is also a subset of users that represent expert information seekers, such as practitioners, educators, students, or policy makers who will still want to make use of scholarly-focused tools, so it is important to maintain support for more traditional protocols like OAI-PMH. These tools are typically built on intermediary metadata aggregators such as CORE, LA Referencia, OpenAIRE, and OpenAlex, which then repurpose the data into more public-facing services. Two examples of such services are OECD AI Policy Observatory, which uses OpenAlex metadata to produce visualisations of AI research trends for policymakers and the wider public (OECD.AI, 2026), and the European Health Information Portal, which harvests structured metadata from health data sources across Europe.

How repositories can improve LLM queries

Large language models (LLMs), which are now starting to dominate most discovery systems, introduce an intrinsic attribution problem that breaks the chain of scholarly credit and verification (Peters & Chin-Yee, 2025). When you ask an LLM a question, it generates an answer by synthesising patterns from the millions of documents it was trained on. But an LLM typically does not track which specific sources contributed to which parts of its response, and, therefore, there is no reliable way to track the claims made in an AI output with the original source material. Recent developments, however, suggest that more structured integrations between repositories and AI systems can go a long way to addressing this issue when they are applied strictly to the scholarly literature. The CORE-GPT project, for example, demonstrated that when AI systems are configured to generate answers using open access articles rather than relying solely on training data, fabricated citations are significantly reduced (Pride et al., 2023). Asai et al. (2026) confirm this at scale with OpenScholar, a retrieval-augmented model drawing on 45 million open-access papers that outperforms GPT-4o in correctness. By contrast, GPT-4o fabricated between 78% and 90% of its cited references when operating without access to the source literature. Similarly, other popular tools such as Google's Gemini or Perplexity are beginning to recognise that there is a user demand for linking to original source material and that this will increase trust of users, particularly for more serious information seekers. In these cases, repositories that expose reliable provenance and structured metadata in machine-friendly ways, the citations will become more transparent to AI systems, which in turn will lead to improving attribution of original sources in their services.

Conclusion

Open access repositories have long been recognised as essential infrastructure for the research community, but their value extends far beyond the academy. Repositories serve very diverse publics, from physicians and educators to entrepreneurs and community

organisers in the Global South, providing barrier-free access to knowledge that would otherwise remain locked behind paywalls.

At a moment when public trust in information is under acute pressure, repositories occupy a uniquely credible position. Their institutional affiliations, transparent governance, and commitment to preserving primary source materials make them reliable anchors in an increasingly turbulent information environment. Yet their potential remains significantly underutilised. Designed primarily for research communities, they have yet to fully embrace the public-facing features that would allow them to reach their full societal impact, such as plain-language summaries, robust provenance signals, and seamless integration with the discovery tools that everyday users actually rely on.

The rapid growth of AI-powered discovery systems makes this challenge both more urgent and more tractable. Repositories that invest in machine-readable metadata, structured provenance, and interoperability with large language models will not only improve attribution and reduce the potential for misinformation, but they will also become foundational to a more trustworthy information ecosystem.

Ultimately, making repositories truly public-facing should not be a technical afterthought. It is a natural extension of the civic mission that universities and research institutions have always held. The knowledge produced through publicly funded research belongs to the public. Repositories are the most direct path to honouring that commitment.

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